

PHYSICAL AND MATHEMATICAL SCIENCES

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INTEGRATING AI INTO THE LEARNING PROCESS OF MATHEMATICS

Abstract.

Modern artificial intelligence (AI) technologies are actively transforming the educational process, making a significant contribution to the methodology of teaching mathematics. This article is an overview of the use of AI in teaching mathematics, aimed at students mastering the basic rules of using AI to solve mathematical problems. The text discusses various aspects of the use of AI, including automation of routine calculations, big data analysis, symbolic and numerical calculations, as well as the contribution of AI to the automatic proof of theorems and optimization of complex systems. Special attention is paid to the methods of teaching students to work with AI, including the development of specific algorithms, the use of training platforms and software.

The article highlights the importance of integrating interactive learning resources such as Khan Academy, Coursera, and edX, which offer courses on AI and machine learning. These resources provide students with access to up-to-date knowledge and practical skills necessary for the successful use of AI in mathematical research.

The use of AI in mathematics lessons opens up new opportunities for a deep understanding of mathematical concepts, promotes the development of critical thinking and analytical abilities of students.

Keywords: artificial intelligence, integration, learning strategies, methods

Introduction: The use of artificial intelligence (AI) in solving mathematical problems is an important and dynamically developing area in modern science and technology. AI is used to solve a wide range of tasks, from basic arithmetic operations to complex problems that require deep analysis and abstract thinking. Explaining to students the use of artificial intelligence (AI) in solving mathematical problems can be organized using various teaching methods and strategies.

Initially, this process can begin with an introduction to the basics of artificial intelligence, explaining what AI is, what types of AI exist and how it is used in solving mathematical problems.

Explanations of various types of AI algorithms and methods, such as machine learning, deep learning, neural networks and their application in mathematics.

Next, you can organize practical classes on the use of AI in the classroom. There may be a variation in the organization of laboratory work, where students can work with AI software and tools such as Python, MATLAB, or specialized platforms for machine learning. Tasks may include solving mathematical problems using libraries such as NumPy, SciPy, TensorFlow or PyTorch.

The final stage may be to present students with real-world examples of the use of AI in mathematics. Discussion of companies and research institutes using AI for data analysis, optimization, financial modeling and other tasks. This will help students see the practical significance and possibilities of AI.

The main part: The use of AI in the learning process has a wide range and can make it much easier to solve difficult tasks.

After all, AI has all types of recognition systems, such as deterministic, probabilistic, logical, structural, combined, etc.[5,18]. Therefore, it is widely used in all areas of mathematics, such as:

1. Automatic theorem proving: AI can analyze and prove mathematical theorems using formal methods and algorithms. Programs such as Coq and Lean enable the automation of evidence and provide support for research and learning.

2. Symbolic computing: Computer systems such as Wolfram Mathematica and Maple use AI to manipulate mathematical expressions and simplify complex formulas. They can solve integrals, differential equations, and more. [3,242-245]

3. Optimization and numerical methods: AI is used to solve optimization problems where it is required to find the best solution among a variety of possible options. Machine learning techniques such as neural networks can predict and analyze data to improve optimization processes.

4. Statistical analysis and data analysis: AI is widely used to analyze large amounts of data, identify patterns and trends, which has direct applications in statistical mathematics and biostatistics.

5. Machine Learning and Data Exploration: Machine learning techniques such as reinforcement learning and unsupervised learning apply mathematical algorithms to train models based on data, which allows you to predict results and make automated decisions.

6. Educational technologies: AI is also used to create adaptive learning systems that analyze the learning process of students and provide individualized tasks to improve understanding of mathematical concepts.

All these examples demonstrate the potential of AI in deepening and expanding the understanding of mathematics, accelerating research and creating new educational tools. The development of AI technologies continues to open up new horizons in mathematics and related disciplines[4]. Continuing the topic of using artificial intelligence in solving mathematical problems, you can delve into several additional aspects and application examples:

7. Solving complex combinatorial problems: AI, especially machine learning algorithms, can be used to solve combinatorial optimization problems such as the traveling salesman problem or the production schedule. AI helps to find acceptable solutions in situations where the exact solution requires excessive computing resources.

8. Artificial neural networks for numerical analysis: Neural networks can be trained to solve differential equations and other numerical analysis problems, which is especially useful in engineering and physical sciences. This makes it possible to model complex systems where traditional numerical methods may be ineffective[2].

9. Cryptography and Security: Artificial intelligence is used in cryptography to analyze and create cryptographic systems, ensure data security and protect against cyber attacks. AI algorithms can help in developing new encryption methods or hacking existing systems.

10. Pattern recognition and Image analysis: AI is used to recognize mathematical symbols and expressions within optical character recognition (OCR) systems. This greatly simplifies the process of entering mathematical data into digital form and their subsequent processing.

11. Predictive Analytics: AI and machine learning are actively used to predict economic and financial trends. Algorithms analyze large amounts of data to predict future market events, which cannot be done with the same accuracy using traditional statistical methods.

12. Robotics and automation: The use of AI to control robotic systems often requires solving complex mathematical problems related to motion control, trajectory planning and optimization of actions in real time.

These examples highlight the importance of integrating artificial intelligence into various fields of mathematics and science. As technology develops and computing power increases, we can expect further expansion of AI capabilities in solving complex and diverse mathematical problems, which will contribute to progress in scientific research and practical application[1,94-97].

Conclusions: The use of artificial intelligence (AI) in teaching mathematics is a powerful tool for empowering both students and teachers.

It encourages students to do independent research and projects related to AI, and allows them to apply theoretical knowledge in practice. The development of algorithms and models for solving mathematical problems contributes not only to a deeper understanding of mathematical concepts, but also to the development of programming skills and analytical thinking.

Engaging experts through guest lectures and webinars enriches the learning process by giving students access to the latest research and innovation in the field of AI. It also helps motivate students and gives them the opportunity to interact with leading experts in the field.

Using platforms such as Khan Academy, Coursera, or edX to study AI and machine learning courses provides students with access to high-quality resources and the opportunity to learn in an interactive format. This promotes independent learning and deepening of knowledge in various fields of mathematics.

Regular discussions and seminars, where students can share ideas and the results of their research, promote critical thinking and the ability to present their thoughts in a reasoned manner. This is important for the formation of a scientific community and the support of collegial feedback.

In general, the integration of AI into the process of teaching mathematics allows not only to improve the understanding of mathematical principles, but also to prepare students for the effective use of modern technologies in their future careers. This makes learning more relevant and attractive for students, opening up new perspectives and opportunities for them.

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